

Conformations of 1,2-Dicyano- and 1,2-Dinitro-substituted Ethanes. A Review

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Manuscript received 3 November 1993

This paper summarises recent work undertaken in our laboratory on the conformations of some 1,2-dicyanoethanes and 1,2-dinitroethanes, and offers a comparison on the conformational properties of these two families of compounds. It brings up to date our work on the 1,2-dinitroethanes which had earlier been reviewed¹. The studies reviewed here form part of an on-going programme to investigate how variations in group size and polarity of substituents affect the conformations of substituted ethanes. In recent years we have focussed our attention on compounds containing cyano or nitro groups. Both the substituents are equally highly polar (with group moments of ca. 13×10^{-30} Cm) but are different in shape, the cyano group being cylindrical and the nitro group angular. The nitro group also has greater spatial requirements than the cyano group.

Of the many types of cyano- and nitroethanes that exist, the 1,2-disubstituted compounds by virtue of their symmetry, are in many ways more amenable to conformational analysis than are those of lower symmetry.

When we began our research in this area, little was known about the conformations of 1,2-dinitroethanes and 1,2-dicyanoethanes. However the conformational data base of these compounds has been expanded over the years providing new insights into their conformational behaviour. The principal physical techniques employed in our laboratory have been infrared

and Raman spectroscopy, Kerr effect and dipole moment measurements on solutions, and X-ray crystallography on solids. The X-ray studies on the solid compounds have been particularly important in establishing the absolute structures of *meso*- and (\pm)-diastereoisomers thereby placing the interpretation of their physicochemical properties on a firm basis. Semi-empirical MO and ab initio quantum mechanical calculations have also been used to help in the elucidation of molecular conformations.

Results

Tables 1 and 2 provide summaries of the results of our studies on the 1,2-dicyanoethanes and 1,2-dinitroethanes. The X-ray results on 2,2,3,3-tetranitrobutane and some AM1 results have not been published before.

Discussion

For the 1,2-dicyano family of compounds, the stable rotational isomers are those shown in Newmann projection in Fig. 1. Some of these compounds can exist as *meso*- and (\pm)-diastereoisomers. For the *meso*-compounds the stable rotamers are (1), (2) and (3) where (1) is the mirror image of (3). For the (\pm)-compounds, the three stable rotational isomers are (4), (5) and (6). Here (4) and (6) are not mirror images of each other. Similar diagrams describe the analogous 1,2-dinitro family of compounds. Fig. 2 shows the stable rotational isomers

TABLE 1—COMPARISON BETWEEN EXPERIMENTAL AND CALCULATED (AM1) VALUES FOR ΔU , DIHEDRAL ANGLE AND % GAUCHE POPULATION OF 1,2-DICYANO DERIVATIVES OF ETHANE

Compd.	Solid state structure ^a	ΔU ($U_g - U_t$) kJ mol ⁻¹		Dihedral angle		% Gauche population		Ref.
		AM1	Expt. ^b	AM1	Expt. ^b	AM1	Expt. ^b	
1,2-Dicyanoethane	<i>trans</i> and <i>gauche</i> above -43.7°	2.89	—	72	93	67	75(B)	4, 5
			6.820		75		26(G)	6
	<i>gauche</i> below -43.7°							
2,3-Dicyano-2,3-dimethylbutane	<i>trans</i> (sp)	4.38	5.48	60	85	25	18,43(B)	8, 9
1,1,2,2-Tetracyanoethane	<i>trans</i> (sp)	1.62	—	69	82	51	53(D)	12, 14
1,2-Dichlorotetracyanoethane	<i>trans</i> (sp)	0.766	—	60	64	59	53	12, 14
<i>meso</i> -1,2-Dicyano-1,2-diphenylethane	<i>trans</i>	7.94	1.67	70	ca. 60	8	51(D)	22, 23
(±)-1,2-Dicyano-1,2-diphenylethane ^c	<i>gauche</i> (6)	-7.58	—	47	60 ^a	97	ca. 100 ^d	22, 23
		-7.27		50				
<i>meso</i> -2,3-Dicyano-2,3-diphenylbutane	<i>trans</i>	4.46	ca. 3.35	60	—	25	ca. 33(D)	25, 26
(±)-2,3-Dicyano-2,3-diphenylbutane ^c	<i>gauche</i> (6)	14.68	—	70	54.6 ^a	50	ca. 26(D)	25, 26
		0.0		60				
<i>meso</i> -3,4-Dicyano-3,4-diphenylhexane	<i>trans</i>	6.99	ca. 4.6	64	—	11	ca. 23(D)	25, 26
(±)-3,4-Dicyano-3,4-diphenylhexane ^c	<i>trans</i> (5)	2.24	—	50	—	63	ca. 27(D)	25, 26
		0.82		60				
<i>meso</i> -2,3-Dicyano-2,3-dicyclopentylbutane	<i>trans</i>	6.16	4.37	54	67	14	26, 45(B)	27
(±)-2,3-Dicyano-2,3-dicyclopentylbutane ^c	<i>gauche</i> (6)	8.63	—	40	49.1 ^a	42	33	27
		0.96		40				
<i>meso</i> -2,3-Dicyano-2,3-bicyclohexylbutane	<i>trans</i>	6.82	6.21	76	97	14	18	28
(±)-2,3-Dicyano-2,3-dicyclohexylbutane ^c	<i>trans</i> (5)	5.65	—	44	—	14	14	28
		6.99		40				
1,1'-Dicyanobicyclopentyl (MMP2 method used)	<i>trans</i>	10.71	9.28	61	85	3	5	29, 30
1,1'-Dicyanobicyclohexyl (MMP2 method used)	<i>trans</i>	11.71	6.60	60	86	2	11	29, 30
1,1'-Dicyanobicycloheptyl (MMP2 method used)	<i>trans</i>	3.51	3.05	52	67	33	38	29, 30

^aDetermined by X-ray crystallography unless stated otherwise. ^bDetermined by dipole moment measurements in solution at different temperatures (Lennard Jones-Pike method) unless stated otherwise. ^cTwo sets of AM1 ΔU and dihedral angles are given as there are two non-equivalent *gauche* conformations (4) and (6). ^dBased on a measured dipole moment of 20.35×10^{-30} Cm in dioxane, not previously reported. (sp) = Based on ir and Raman spectroscopy. (—) = Not measurable in the case of (±)-isomers; also because of limited solubility or because the *gauche* population is nearly at its saturation point. (B), (D) = Measured in benzene (B) or dioxane (D) solution. (G) = Gaseous state. MMP2 = Molecular mechanics methods.

that arise when two bonds of each central carbon atom form part of a cycloalkyl ring.

Tables 1 and 2 list three physical quantities of interest : (i) ΔU , the internal energy difference between the *gauche* and *trans* rotamers, (ii) the dihedral angle of the *gauche* rotamer (when

available) and (iii) the percentage *gauche* population for the dicyano and dinitro compounds studied. In principle, all three quantities can be obtained experimentally from dipole moment measurements alone on solutions at different temperatures followed by a Lennard Jones-Pike analysis² (for compounds

TABLE 2—COMPARISON BETWEEN EXPERIMENTAL AND CALCULATED (AM1) VALUES FOR ΔU , DIHEDRAL ANGLE AND % GAUCHE POPULATION OF 1,2-DINITRO DERIVATIVES OF ETHANE

Compd.	Solid state structure ^a	ΔU ($U_g - U_t$) kJ mol ⁻¹		Dihedral angle in degree for gauche rotamer		% Gauche population		Ref.
		AM1	Expt ^b	AM1	Expt ^b	AM1	Expt. ^b	
		1,2-Dinitroethane	<i>gauche</i>	-6.35	-4.33	70	73.5 ^a	
2-Methyl-1,2-dinitropropane	<i>gauche</i> (sp)	-6.53	-7.17	66	82	96	88	19
2,3-Dinitro-2,3-dimethylbutane	<i>gauche</i>	1.62	2.48	60	93	51	42,79(B)	9,10
2,2,3,3-Tetranitrobutane	<i>gauche</i>	3.03	3.35	50	83	37	34,72(B)	12,14
<i>meso</i> -1,2-Dinitro-1,2-diphenylethane	<i>trans</i>	29.12	—	60	—	0.1	ca.11(B)	16,23
(±)-1,2-Dinitro-1,2-diphenylethane ^c	<i>gauche</i> (4)	-20.13 -18.16	—	68 40	50.6 ^a	99.9	ca.100	16,23
<i>meso</i> -2,3-Dinitro-2,3-diphenylbutane	<i>gauche</i>	-6.27	—	60	56.5 ^a	96	ca.88	16,23
(±)-2,3-Dinitro-2,3-diphenylbutane ^c	<i>gauche</i> (4)	-13.06 -6.19	—	58 42	42.8 ^a	99.5	ca.100	16,23
<i>meso</i> -3,4-Dinitro-3,4-dimethylhexane	<i>gauche</i>	0.29	1.51	60	80	64	53,80(B)	15
1,1'-Dinitrobicyclopentyl	<i>gauche</i>	-1.69	-2.25	58	67	80	83	17,18
1,1'-Dinitrobicyclohexyl	<i>gauche</i>	1.44	2.59	59	90	53	42	17,18
1,1'-Dinitrobicycloheptyl	<i>gauche</i>	5.82	5.99	57	64	16	16	17,18

^aDetermined by X-ray crystallography unless stated otherwise. ^bDetermined by dipole moment measurements in solution at different temperatures (Lennard Jones-Pike method) unless stated otherwise. ^cTwo sets of AM1 ΔU and dihedral angles are given as there are two non-equivalent *gauche* conformations (4) and (6). ^dBased on a measured dipole moment of 20.35×10^{-30} Cm in dioxane, not previously reported. (sp) = Based on ir and Raman spectroscopy. (—) = Not measurable in the case of (±)-isomers; also because of limited solubility or because the *gauche* population is nearly at its saturation point. (B) = Measured in benzene solution.

of the type R — $\begin{array}{c} \text{X} \quad \text{X} \\ | \quad | \\ \text{C} \text{---} \text{C} \\ | \quad | \\ \text{R} \quad \text{R} \end{array}$ — R). Alternatively,

the dihedral angle of the *gauche* rotamer and the percentage *gauche* population can be obtained by combining dipole moment with Kerr effect measurements at one temperature¹. For (±)-diastereoisomers, these methods although not strictly applicable, can still be used if the rotamers (4) and (6) are approximately equal in moment. These physical quantities can also be obtained by theoretical methods for both *meso*- and (±)-compounds from graphical plots of calculated molecular energies against the dihedral angle X-C-C-X. Typical plots for a pair of *meso*- and (±)-isomers based on AM1 parametrisation

are shown in Figs. 3 and 4. The physical quantities of interest may be extracted from these plots as follows. The isomeric ratio N_g/N_t for a *meso*-compound consisting of an equilibrium mixture of non-interacting species (1), (2) and (3) (see Fig. 1) can be evaluated from the Boltzmann equation, $N_g/N_t = 2 \exp(-\Delta U/RT)$ where $\Delta U = U_g - U_t$, is the energy difference between the *gauche* and *trans* rotamers. By analogy, the distribution in the gas phase of the rotamers (4), (5) and (6) in any racemic compound of the type shown in Fig. 1, is governed by a similar Boltzmann equation,

$$(4) : (5) : (6) = \exp(-\Delta U_1/RT) : 1 : \exp(-\Delta U_2/RT)$$

where $\Delta U_1 = U_{g1} - U_t$ and $\Delta U_2 = U_{g2} - U_t$, the symbols *g* and *t* referring to *gauche* and *trans*. The dihedral angle of the *gauche* rotamer can

gauche (1)

trans (2)

meso - isomer

gauche (3)

gauche (1)

trans (2)

gauche (3)

Fig. 2. *Trans* and *gauche* conformers of 1,1'-dicyano-bicyclopentyl ($n = 2$), 1,1'-dicyano-bicyclohexyl ($n = 3$) and 1,1'-dicyano-bicycloheptyl ($n = 4$) where $R = (CH_2)_n$.

gauche (4)

trans (5)

(±) - isomer

gauche (6)

Fig. 1. Newmann projections for the *trans* and *gauche* conformers of *meso*- and (±)-1,2-dicyanoethanes, where $X = H, CN, Me, Et$, and $R = H, Cl, Me, Ph, cyclopentyl, cyclohexyl$.

be read off from the appropriate energy minimum. This theoretical approach has been used to calculate the three physical quantities listed under AM1 in Tables 1 and 2 for comparison with the experimentally determined values. For the (±)-compounds, however, the individual populations of the rotamers (4) and (6) cannot be separated from each other when analysing the dielectric measurements. Only an approximate value of the combined populations of the *gauche* rotamers (4) and (6) can be estimated from the experimental data, by assuming that the moments of (4) and (6) are the same. Thus, for ease of comparison,

Fig. 3. Energy of *meso*-1,2-dinitro-1,2-diphenylethane as a function of the N-C-C-N torsion angle calculated using AM1 parametrisation.

the *gauche* populations for the (\pm)-compounds in Tables 1 and 2 calculated by semi-empirical MO theory, are presented as combined populations for the *gauche* rotamers (4) and (6). In this paper, the term '*gauche* population' for (\pm)-compounds is used in this sense. More details on the methods of evaluation mentioned earlier are given in reference 1. It should also be pointed out that the experimental results reported here are for the 'inert' solvent carbon tetrachloride, unless stated otherwise. When benzene or dioxane is used as solvent, there is usually a solvent-induced stabilisation of the *gauche* rotamers which results in an increase in the population of this rotamer and hence an augmentation of the measured dipole moment.

The most striking feature from Tables 1 and 2, is that with the exceptions of 1,2-dicyanoethane, *meso*-1,2-dinitro-1,2-diphenylethane and the (\pm)-compounds, all the 1,2-dicyanoethanes exist in the *trans* conformation, whereas all the 1,2-dinitroethanes exist in the *gauche* conformation in the solid state.

Wolfe³ pointed out that there is a tendency for a structure which has the maximum number of *gauche* interactions between the adjacent electron pairs and/or polar bonds to be favoured. In the case of the dinitroethanes each nitro group has a very high polarity and possesses two non-bonding electron pairs on each oxygen atom and one electron pair on the nitrogen atom. Thus the attractive forces between the adjacent electron pairs on *gauche* nitro groups appear to be the overriding factor in determining the conformations of the dinitroethanes. However, the final conformation adopted is still dependent on the overall balance of the attraction and repulsion between the groups in a given molecule. The case of 1,2-dinitro-1,2-diphenylethane, which favours the *trans* conformation even in the solid state, illustrates this point (see below). By contrast, the cyano group which has only one electron pair on its nitrogen atom does not appear to exert as powerful an attraction on an adjacent (*gauche*) cyano group. Consequently the preferred conformation is the *trans*.

Fig 4 Energy of (\pm)-1,2-dinitro-1,2-diphenylethane as a function of the N-C-C-N torsion angle calculated using AM1 parametrisation.

When dioxane is the solvent, an augmentation in dipole moment is observed.

1,2-Dicyanoethane and 1,2-dinitroethane :

1,2-Dicyanoethane and 1,2-dinitroethane, the two prototype molecules of the 1,2-dicyano and 1,2-dinitro families of compounds, differ in two important respects : they adopt different conformations from each other in the solid state, and in solution their *gauche* and *trans* population distributions are also significantly different. Thus Fitzgerald and Janz⁴ showed by spectroscopic measurements that above -43.7° , 1,2-dicyanoethane exists as a mixture of *trans* and *gauche* rotamers in the solid state but that below this temperature, only the *gauche* rotamer is present. Le Fevre *et al.*⁵ showed by dipole moment and Kerr effect measurements that in benzene solution, a mixture of *gauche* and *trans* rotamers exists in equilibrium in the ratio 75 : 25 with the *gauche* predominating. From their electron diffraction study⁶ Fernholt and Kveseth concluded that gaseous 1,2-dicyanoethane exists mainly in the *trans* conformation (74%) at 170° with an energy separation between the *gauche* and *trans* rotamer of $6.820 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$. By contrast, 1,2-dinitroethane exists in the *gauche* conformation in the solid state and the *gauche* content in benzene solution is about 92%⁷. AM1 calculations gave results which agree rather well with experimental observations for benzene solution in the case of 1,2-dinitroethane but less well in the case of 1,2-dicyanoethane. Agreement with electron diffraction results for 1,2-dicyanoethane is poor.

2,3-Dicyano-2,3-dimethylbutane and 2,3-dinitro-2,3-dimethylbutane :

On replacing the four hydrogen atoms in 1,2-dicyanoethane and in 1,2-dinitroethane by methyl groups, we obtain 2,3-dicyano-2,3-dimethylbutane and 2,3-dinitro-2,3-dimethylbutane. Whilst this substitution has no effect on the conformations adopted in the solid state (still *trans* for

the dicyano^{8,9} and still *gauche* for the dinitro compound^{10,11}), in benzene solution the proportion of the *gauche* rotamer is reduced in 2,3-dinitro-2,3-dimethylbutane (from 75 to 43%)⁹ and in 2,3-dinitro-2,3-dimethylbutane (from 92 to 79%)¹¹. From Tables 1 and 2 we see that AM1-calculated *gauche* populations for 2,3-dicyano-2,3-dimethylbutane and 2,3-dinitro-2,3-dimethylbutane are in better agreement with the observed values in carbon tetrachloride, an inert solvent, than in benzene where specific solute-solvent interactions are known to exist. However, a similar comparison for 1,2-dicyanoethane and 1,2-dinitroethane is not possible as these compounds are not soluble in non-polar solvents other than benzene. Nevertheless it seems likely that the *gauche* populations of these two compounds in an inert solvent like carbon tetrachloride will be smaller than their corresponding values in benzene.

1,1,2,2-Tetracyanoethane and 2,2,3,3-tetranitrobutane :

The presence of four symmetrically substituted cyano or nitro groups in the molecule has the effect of reducing the *gauche* population from 75% in 1,2-dicyanoethane in benzene solution to 53% in 1,1,2,2-tetracyanoethane in dioxane and decreasing the *gauche* population from 92% in 1,2-dinitroethane to 72% in 2,2,3,3-tetranitrobutane in benzene solution. The solid state structures for 1,1,2,2-tetracyanoethane and 2,2,3,3-tetranitrobutane remain *trans* and *gauche* respectively¹²⁻¹⁵. It was concluded¹³ that 2,2,3,3-tetranitrobutane exists as a mixture of 66% of the *trans* and 34% of *gauche* rotamer in carbon tetrachloride solution at 25° . It was also suggested that some of the observed weak spectral bands of the solid could be attributed to the presence of the *trans* rotamer in the solid state in addition to the *gauche*. The suggested presence of the *trans* rotamer was based mainly on the fact that no additional bands were seen on dissolving the solid in organic solvents. How-

ever our X-ray crystal diffraction study now shows that the absolute structure of 2,2,3,3-tetranitrobutane is *gauche* and that there is no other species in the solid (there is no disorder in the crystal structure)¹⁵. Consequently, the earlier inference that both the *gauche* and *trans* rotamers are present in the solid state, is partly mistaken. All the ir and Raman bands in the solid state spectra must therefore be assigned to vibrations of the *gauche* rotamer. At the same time, our dielectric data show that in solution, the proportion of *trans* rotamer is quite high, 66% in carbon tetrachloride and 28% in benzene at 25°. The fact that no additional bands were seen on dissolving the solid in an organic solvent must therefore mean that the *trans* bands in solution are not distinguishable from the *gauche* bands within the limits of resolution of the spectrophotometer, i.e. they may be masked by, or coincide in frequency with the *gauche* bands. AM1 results gave reasonably good agreement with the physical quantities derived from the dielectric measurements.

Meso-3,4-dinitro-3,4-dimethylhexane compared with 2,3-dinitro-2,3-dimethylbutane :

3,4-Dinitro-3,4-dimethylhexane exists in two diastereoisomeric forms : the *meso* and the (\pm). The physical measurements carried out on these two forms of the compound have been interpreted on the assumption that the *meso* was the compound with the higher and the (\pm) compound with the lower melting point¹⁶. This assumption however needs to be confirmed by single crystal X-ray crystallography. On this assumption, one can tentatively conclude from the spectroscopic data that *meso-3,4-dinitro-3,4-dimethylhexane* exists in the *gauche* conformation in the solid state. The dielectric data for the *meso*-isomer suggest that despite being sterically more hindered than 2,3-dinitro-2,3-dimethylbutane, there is only a small change in the *gauche* population in carbon tetrachloride solution : from 42% to

53%. This small increase is consistent with the results of AM1 calculations. In benzene solution, the *gauche* population is 80%, little different from the corresponding value in 2,3-dinitro-2,3-dimethylbutane (79% *gauche*).

Unfortunately, the analogous dicyano compound has not yet been studied, so a comparison is not yet possible.

Meso- and (\pm)-1,2-dicyano-1,2-diphenylethane compared with meso- and (\pm)-1,2-dinitro-1,2-diphenylethane :

X-Ray diffraction results confirm that for 1,2-dinitro-1,2-diphenylethane the compound with the higher melting point (239–240°) is the *meso* isomer and that with the lower melting point (153–154°) the racemic form¹⁷. In the *meso*-isomer all the substituent groups are *trans* to each other in the solid. In (\pm)-1,2-dinitro-1,2-diphenylethane, the molecule as a whole adopts in the solid the conformation shown as (4) in Fig. 1 where the nitro groups are *gauche*. In this conformation, the phenyl groups are also *gauche* while the two H atoms are *trans* to each other. The fact that the *meso*-isomer adopts a *trans* conformation in the solid rather than the *gauche* is in striking contrast to all the vicinal dinitroethanes studied so far^{7,11,18–20} (Table 2).

In all these other instances the two nitro groups have invariably been found to be *gauche* in the solid state. The *gauche* rotamer also tends to predominate in solution. This preference for the *gauche* conformation has been attributed to the so called *gauche* effect³ mentioned earlier. However, in the case of *meso-1,2-dinitro-1,2-diphenylethane*, the dominant influence of this effect on conformation appears to have been overcome by some other factor(s).

One possible offsetting factor that needs to be considered is the intramolecular attraction that should exist at van der Waals distances between

the H and Ph and between the H and NO₂ groups, caused by the acidic nature of the H atoms attached to the central C-C bond²¹, the electron-deficient hydrogens being attracted by electron-rich groups such as nitro and phenyl. Support for this hypothesis can be found in our MO calculations. Indeed, an analysis of the intramolecular non-bonded interaction energies calculated with AM1 parametrisation shows that such attractions are not only predicted, but are also maximised in the *trans* rotamer, thus suggesting these to be the main cause of the *trans* being more stable than the *gauche* rotamer.

Like *meso*-1,2-dinitro-1,2-diphenylethane, *meso*-1,2-dicyano-1,2-diphenylethane adopts the *trans* conformation in the solid state while in the (±)-compound the two cyano groups are *gauche* [structure (6) in Fig. 1] with the phenyl groups *trans*²².

AM1 calculations with full geometry optimisation predict that *meso*-1,2-dicyano-1,2-diphenylethane should exist almost exclusively in the *trans* conformation (92%) in the gas phase. However, the proportion of *trans* molecules observed in dioxane solution is moderate, about 49%²³ probably because of preferential solvent-induced stabilisation of the *gauche* rotamer. This contrasts with *meso*-1,2-dinitro-1,2-diphenylethane²⁴ which exists in benzene solution mainly in the *trans* conformation, about 89%. On the other hand, it is noteworthy that in both (±)-1,2-dinitro-1,2-diphenylethane and (±)-1,2-dicyano-1,2-diphenylethane, the proportion of *gauche* molecules in solution is almost 100%^{23,24}, indicating the much greater stability of the conformation where the cyano or nitro substituents are *gauche* [(4) and (6)], over the conformation where these substituents are *trans* [conformer (5)].

Meso- and (±)-2,3-dicyano-2,3-diphenylbutane compared with meso- and (±)-3,4-dicyano-3,4-diphenylhexane and meso- and (±)-2,3-dinitro-2,3-diphenylbutane :

Conformational analysis of 2,3-dicyano-2,3-diphenylbutane showed abnormal dipole moment behaviour²⁵, viz. the *meso*-isomer has a higher dipole moment than the (±)-form unlike the values for the corresponding stilbene dichloride diastereoisomers. This could only come about if the dipolar repulsion between the C-CN dipoles overrides the steric interactions between the phenyl groups in importance. This situation is however reversed in 3,4-dicyano-3,4-diphenylhexane, i.e. the racemic (±)- has a higher moment than the *meso*-isomer as expected for phenyl-substituted succinonitriles, showing that the polar interactions are to some extent offset by the bulkier ethyl groups. However, these conclusions are valid only if the assignment of the *meso*- and (±)-forms on the basis that the compound with the higher melting point is the *meso*- and that with the lower melting point the (±)-isomer, is correct. Our molecular structure determinations by X-ray diffraction methods confirm that in both pairs of diastereoisomers, it is the *meso* form that has the higher melting point and the (±)-form the lower melting point²⁶. In the solid state, *meso*-2,3-dicyano-2,3-diphenylbutane, *meso*-3,4-dicyano-3,4-diphenylhexane and (±)-3,4-dicyano-3,4-diphenylhexane adopt the *trans* conformation with respect to the cyano groups while in (±)-2,3-dicyano-2,3-diphenylbutane the cyano groups are *gauche* [structure (4) in Fig. 1]²⁶.

By contrast, our X-ray study has now established that in the compounds *meso*- and (±)-2,3-dinitro-2,3-diphenylbutane the two nitro groups are *gauche* in the solid state, viz. (1) or (3) and (4) respectively. Furthermore, contrary to normal expectation the *meso*-compound (140–141°) has a lower melting point than the racemate (148–149°)¹⁷. The reported dipole moment data²⁴ therefore need to be reinterpreted. The correct moment for *meso*-2,3-dinitro-2,3-diphenylbutane is now 17.48×10^{-30} Cm in carbon tetrachloride and 17.88×10^{-30} Cm in benzene corresponding to a *gauche* population

of about 88% at 25°. The correct moment for (\pm)-2,3-dinitro-2,3-diphenylbutane is 20.35×10^{-30} Cm in carbon tetrachloride and 20.45×10^{-30} Cm in benzene corresponding to a *gauche* population of about 100% at 25°. In *meso*- and (\pm)-2,3-dicyano-2,3-diphenylbutane, the *gauche* population is much lower, about 33 and 26% respectively²³. These variations are generally corroborated by the AM1 results in the case of the 2,3-dinitro-2,3-diphenylbutanes, but are less successfully reproduced in the case of 2,3-dicyano-2,3-diphenylbutanes possibly because of an irregular dioxane solvent effect.

Meso- and (\pm)-2,3-dicyano-2,3-dicyclopentylbutane compared with meso- and (\pm)-2,3-dicyano-2,3-dicyclohexylbutane :

These two sets of compounds contain two large groups in each molecule. In going from pentyl to hexyl in the *meso*-compounds, there is no change in the preferred solid state conformation of *trans* although there is a small reduction in the proportion of the *gauche* conformer in carbon tetrachloride solution (from 25 to 18%)^{27,28}. However, in the case of the (\pm)-compounds, whilst the conformation adopted by (\pm)-2,3-dicyano-2,3-dicyclopentylbutane in the solid state is one in which the cyano groups are *gauche*, shown as structure (6) in Fig. 1, the solid state conformation of (\pm)-2,3-dicyano-2,3-dihexylbutane is quite different, being structure (5) with the cyano groups *trans*. The proportion of the *gauche* population in carbon tetrachloride solution is also reduced from 33 to 14%. Thus substituting the pentyl group by the bulkier hexyl, appears to have the effect of stabilising the '*trans*' conformer (5) both in the solid and in solution. The relative proportions in solution are also reflected in the AM1 results.

Comparison between 1,1'-dicyano- and 1,1'-dinitrobicycloalkanes :

The Newmann projections for the dicyano compounds (bipentyl, bihexyl and biheptyl) are

shown in Fig. 2. They are also applicable to the corresponding dinitro compounds.

All three dicyano compounds are in the *trans* conformation²⁹. The cyclopentyl ring adopts the 'envelope' structure while the cyclohexyl and cycloheptyl rings are in the chair conformation. The structures of 1,1'-dicyanobicyclopentyl and 1,1'-dicyanobicycloheptyl belong to the C_{2h} point group while that of 1,1'-dicyanobicyclohexyl is of approximate C_{2h} symmetry. The central C(1)-C(1') bond length increases with ring size as a result of increasing steric congestion.

On the other hand, the shape of the polar substituent in the dinitro analogues is angular rather than cylindrical. As expected, this causes greater steric congestion. These dinitro-bicycloalkanes adopt *gauche* conformations with the nitro groups in close proximity¹⁹. As the ring size increases, the strain arising from contacts between the nitro groups increases and is reflected in increasing inter-ring and C-N bond lengths. The cyclopentyl ring adopts a skewed structure rather than the 'envelope' form. The cyclohexyl and cycloheptyl rings adopt chair conformations, as in 1,1-dicyano-bicyclohexyl and 1,1'-dicyano-bicycloheptyl, but are of lower symmetry.

All three dinitro-bicycloalkanes adopt *gauche* conformations in the solid state with the nitro groups in close proximity. The cyclopentyl rings adopt skew conformations. The cyclohexyl rings adopt chair conformations with both rings attached by a bond which is equatorial to both rings. Using the notation from the literature¹⁹, the cycloheptyl rings adopt chair-like conformations characterised by the near coplanarity of the atoms C(3), C(4), C(5) and C(6) which form the 'back' of the chair and atoms C(2), C(3), C(6) and C(7) which form the seat of the chair. As the ring size increases the strain arising from contacts between the nitro groups increases and is reflected in increasing inter-ring and C-N bond lengths.

The differences in rotational isomeric behaviour in carbon tetrachloride solution between the 1,1'-dinitrobicycloalkanes and the 1,1'-dicyanobicycloalkanes are brought out clearly in Tables 1 and 2. In the dinitro series, a steady increase in the magnitude of ΔU is observed from the five to the seven-membered ring compounds, reflecting the decrease of the *gauche* population from 83 to 16% as ring size increases. In the dicyano series, the opposite trend is observed with the ΔU value decreasing and the *gauche* population increasing from 4.5 to 38% as the ring size increases³⁰.

Although AM1 calculations gave results which were in satisfactory agreement with experiment in the dinitro series this was not the case in the dicyano series. We therefore carried out molecular mechanics calculations³¹ as an alternative approach which, as Tables 1 and 2 show, gave good predictions in the case of 1,1'-dicyanobicyclopentyl and 1,1'-dicyanobicycloheptyl, but were less successful with 1,1'-dicyanobicyclopentyl.

As may be expected, the calculated barrier to internal rotation from the *gauche* to the *trans* form increases with ring size within each series. It is also significant that, in the solid state, the dinitro compounds exist in the *gauche* conformation whereas the dicyano compounds, based on our X-ray evidence appear to prefer the *trans* conformation.

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